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D6.5 Checklists, factsheets and gender glossary

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INTRODUCTION

Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN transition (RE4GREEN) is a three-year project funded by the European Union's Horizon Grants for research. The project aims to develop a framework that will address **ethics and integrity concerns** within the green transition. **Women Engage for a Common Future** is an **ecofeminist** network organisation and a partner on the RE4GREEN project, whose role is predominantly to **strengthen the capacity of the partners** to implement ecofeminist analysis and action throughout the project's implementation.

The United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development sets out 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs), which focus on key goals for sustainability the Member States should work towards. The SDGs are interconnected, as is shown in the factsheet here, issues of **health** (SDG 3), **gender** (SDG 5) and **climate change** (SDG 13) are **impossible** to address in **siloe**d approaches. At the same time, the European Union historically has not made such connections, for example the **European Green Deal** does little to incorporate the socially transformative analysis that was outlined in *inter alia* the **EU's Gender Equality Strategy** and the **Anti Racism Action Plan**.

With this context in mind then, and also considering **RE4GREEN's aims** as well as **positionality** as an EU funded project, the subsequent documents aim to **stimulate discussion** among the consortium for how we can address structural inequalities within the green transition. **The glossary** outlines key definitions that will be worked with throughout the capacity strengthening, and the **fact sheet** gives entry points for thinking about the connection between social identities, the green transition, and research ethics. The **two factsheets** provide areas for reflection on report writing, in order to understand how the research we do can reproduce inequalities. **These documents will provide a basis for future consortium training** for the partners to engage with ecofeminist issues as they arise both in the project implementation and in thinking about the green transition more broadly.

GLOSSARY

No definition is neutral, and the definitions given below are based on the positionality of the authors. This is a living document and will be edited as the RE4GREEN project develops.

Coloniality refers to discourses and practices that reproduce **racial-colonial power relations** and structures. **Quijano (2000)** coined the term to provide an analytical frame for understanding how racial classifications shape modernity. This means the classification of colonised people's ways of being and thinking are considered **naturally inferior** to White European colonisers'. An example of this is how **Western liberal democratic values** continue to be imposed and used as a gauge that all countries are measured up against.

Coloniality and Gender **Lugones (2010)** gives an illuminating history of gender as a colonial construct, as colonised people were constructed as 'having' a sex, but not having a gender. She argues that gender was inexplicably bound up with ideas of temporality; the **"civilised coloniser"** versus the **"backwards colonial subject."** By constructing the colonised subject as sexed, they could be sexualised, which led to both the creation of the "over sexual colonised female" and the "feminine colonised male" who could be controlled through, inter alia, sexual violence. **Gender was something that was achieved** for those who became civilised under the colonial ideal of the European man (and to a lesser extent the European woman), through which colonised peoples were subverted.

Hetero Patriarchy is the social system we live in, in which **men hold power**, predominating in roles of political leadership, moral authority, social privilege, and control of property. Patriarchy is based on a **dichotomous binary distinction** between men and women, where the differences between both categories become naturalised. For example, **men are portrayed as being "rational" and women are contrasted as "emotional"**, this means that men's expression of emotions are understood to be more logical and these characteristics are considered more valuable. At the same time, **heterosexism pairs together men and women**, meaning any experiences of gender or sexuality out of this binary distinction are suppressed and made unnatural. This is why many scholars and activists have used the word **"queer"** to explain their ways of challenging this binary system of heteropatriarchy.

Neo/liberal Feminism Liberal feminism **centres** the **experience of whiteness** and the experiences of women in the colonial core. It argues for "giving a voice to the voiceless" where white women in Europe **dictate an understanding of what the goals of feminism should be**. Neoliberal Feminism is hyper individualised and focuses on **individual women's "empowerment"** and ability to succeed in a neoliberal world.

Ecofeminism is a movement that combines **ecological sustainability** and feminist principles, arguing that the exploitation of nature and the oppression of women are interconnected. It emphasises that **environmental degradation** and **social inequality** are both rooted in **patriarchal** and **capitalist** systems, and calls for the **dismantling of these structures** to promote justice for both the environment and marginalised communities. Ecofeminists advocate for a holistic approach that integrates environmental care with the pursuit of gender equality and social justice.

Environmental Justice is an approach to environmental politics that addresses the impacts of **colonialism** and **capitalism** on the environment. This includes ensuring that **wealthy colonial countries bear (financial) responsibility** for the climate crisis as well as acknowledging that those who live in the **global periphery often bear the brunt** of the impacts of climate change.

Intersectionality as a term was first coined by Black legal scholar **Kimberle Crenshaw in 1989**. Crenshaw highlighted how African American women could make claims of **discrimination under sexism or racism but not both**. Crenshaw then expanded this work to highlight the **intersection** of the identities of "Black" and "Woman" in the specific context of the U.S. Since then, intersectionality has become uplifted into many contexts within feminist writing. This is **something to be wary of** in some cases, for example additive intersectionality is a **"diversity within"** model, whereby a predefined social group (e.g., women) is sought to be expanded on through **"diversity" principles**. This model assumes that merely adding more diverse groups into a space will automatically address the structural issues of racism within that space. Such work does not tackle the hegemonic status quo of white liberal feminism. **(Christoffersen and Emejulu, 2023)**

De-colonialism examines the ways in which **western modernity has made natural western domination**. It is linked to Latin American scholars **Lugones** and **Quijano**, as well as world systems theory. Through "delinking" (see **Mignolo 2007**), de-colonialism offers new ways to reimagine a world that is a radical alternative to the colonial one we exist in today.

Post-colonialism seeks to analyse colonial discourse and culture using a lens that unpacks and fundamentally challenges the way the colonial subject is presented in western discourses. It was developed by scholars such as **Edward Said, Homi Bhabha, and Gayatri Spivak**.

Standpoint Theory is a **feminist application of Marxist theory** that indicates the 'consciousness' as an oppressed group in understanding both the position of the oppressed, the advantages of an oppressor and the process of recognising that others suffer the same forms of oppression as you.

Gender Transformative Approaches are strategies and interventions aimed at **transforming gender relations** to promote equity and to challenge structural heteropatriarchy. Often facilitated through collecting **gender-disaggregated data**, to address the data gap and understand gendered realities. Gender transformative policies **go further than gender sensitive policies** (which reflect awareness of gender inequalities), and **gender responsive policies** (which aim to address gender inequalities).

Gender Mainstreaming is the practice of assessing and addressing the **gendered implications** of any planned action, including **legislation, policies, or programs**, to ensure that gender equality is considered and promoted.

Feminist Facilitation Techniques Methods used in group discussions and trainings that prioritise **accessible, inclusive, and equitable** engagement, often highlighting the voices and **experiences of marginalised groups**. [See our feminist moderation course.](#)

FURTHER READING

Below are some further readings as well as texts referenced in this Glossary. Those that have a clickable link are journal articles, and those without are books.

Ecofeminism

- Ourkiya, Asmae (2020) "[Queering Ecofeminism: Towards an Anti-Far-Right Environmentalism](#)"
- MacGregor, Sherilyn (2004) "[From Care to Citizenship: Calling Ecofeminism Back to Politics](#)"

De-colonialism

- Lugones, María (2010) "[Toward a Decolonial Feminism](#)"
- Mignolo, Walter (2007) "[DELINKING: The rhetoric of modernity, the logic of coloniality and the grammar of de-coloniality](#)"
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Post-colonialism

- Bhaba, Homi (1984) "Representation and the colonial text: a critical exploration of some forms of mimeticism". In: Frank Groversmith (ed.), *The Theory of Reading*.
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Intersectionality

- Crenshaw, Kimberle (1989) "[Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics](#)"
- Christoffersen, Ashlee and Emejulu, Akwugo (2023) "["Diversity Within": The Problems with "Intersectional" White Feminism in Practice](#)"

Factsheet: Linking Gender, Climate Change and Research

What is Ecofeminism?

Ecofeminism argues that the **structures that created the climate crisis** also create **gendered social injustice**. For example, colonialism and **patriarchy** create a hierarchy that prioritises the **non-disabled white European man** and **subverts** people of other categories such as **women in all their diversity, queer people, disabled people and people of colour**. At the same time, white European men were the principal actors in the **rapid industrialisation of Europe** through the violent **exploitation of colonies**, and the subsequent environmental destruction and climate crisis. Through violently extracting **natural resources** as well as the **labour of people** from the colonies, Europe continues to foster its own expansion and development whilst ensuring colonised countries **do not** have access to the **resources to tackle climate change**. This means that structurally excluded communities who are most impacted by climate change are at the **forefront** of the **ecofeminist** fight for a gender and climate just future.

Differentiated Impact of Climate Change and Environmental Degradation in Europe

The differentiated impacts of climate change are not just confined to disparities between the Global North and South but also manifest within Europe by disproportionately impacting those groups who continue to be excluded from Europe's development.

→ **LGBTQ+ people and community enclaves** are disproportionately located in high-risk areas prone to **flooding, poor air quality, mosquito-borne diseases, and extreme heat**, all of which are scenarios that are increasing due to climate change. ([source](#))

→ The EU's agricultural free trade agreements lead to **mechanised cash cropping**, which **crowds women out of the farms** in which they hold knowledge. At the same time, these policies negatively impact the climate through **deforestation, reduction of biodiversity and greenhouse gas emissions**. ([source](#) - p. 71)

→ Skin lightening creams are marketed to (primarily) women of colour to achieve the **European beauty standard of whiteness**. Such creams are ill regulated on the EU market and have been found to contain high traces of **mercury** which can cause **psychological and skin disorders** as well as being **damaging** to the **environment**. ([source](#) - p. 138)

→ Women often make **several shorter trips** on public transport (known as **trip chaining**), while men are more likely to travel from **point A to B**. This is because women's trip patterns are more likely to revolve around care e.g., taking children to school, looking after older relatives, or household grocery shopping. Whereas men are more likely to go to work and then return. Yet the design of the **EU's green transport policies** continues to be based on **masculine mobility patterns**. ([source](#) - p16)

→ **Older women** are more disproportionately affected by **energy poverty** – as due to the **pension gap** and the **gender pay gap**, they are more likely to be unable to **afford to heat** their homes, as well as being **more sensitive to heat and cold** stresses due to their physiology, and more at **risk of death** from heat related conditions (if they were assigned female at birth). ([source](#))

Ecofeminism and Research Ethics

Traditional research methodology assumes a **"researcher"** and an **"object"** of study. In much of the research around the effects of climate change, **nature and the environment** are treated as an object of study. Similarly, **communities who are most affected by climate change** are also treated as objects of study within academia. The colonial structure of academia means that the most prestigious research institutes with the most funding are based in the Global North. Additionally, due to **patriarchal structures**, and despite numerous initiatives to improve the representation of women, the senior positions are still dominated by white men. When researching the Global South, often the **"data"** of objects of study are **taken from their context by researchers based in the Global North** for their own academic profit, with **little to no benefit** accruing to research participants in the Global South.

Structural Inequality and Research Ethics

Whilst there have been efforts to develop new research paradigms to tackle the colonial and patriarchal structures in academia, many of the structural issues remain. These can be illustrated in persisting structural barriers, research gaps and inequalities in what is considered “valid” research.

➔ A study on journals published in the Web of Science directory found that over half of journals **come from just 5 countries** (UK, US, New Zealand, Australia, Canada), with **96.17% publishing in English only**. ([source](#))

➔ A study on patterns of authorship over the period 2005–2015 in ‘leading’ economics journals that publish regularly on Africa found that while the journals have **30% of their content about Africa**, **only 3% of their editorial boards are based on the continent**. ([source](#))

➔ In Europe, although **women** represent nearly **half of grade C positions** (researcher, assistant professor), **grade A positions** that include full professors and directors of research comprised only **26.2% women in 2018**. ([source](#))

➔ While **work-related cancers** cause many deaths every year due to chemical exposure, those that occur in **male dominated fields** (e.g., mining) remain a research focus, whereas **women dominated** sectors (e.g., nail salons in Europe/the USA that are made up of primarily women migrant workers from East Asia) remain under-researched. When research is conducted, it is rarely on chronic/long term exposure and takes **75 kilo white men aged 25-36 as the basis of study**. (source - Invisible Women, Chapter 5)

Those Most Affected at the Forefront of Change!

Whilst we cannot immediately eradicate colonial and patriarchal dynamics in our work, we can highlight initiatives where those most affected are at the forefront of change, and rethink traditional extractive approaches of “researcher” versus “the researched”.

→ The **Indigenous Saami people** of Sweden have been at the forefront in organising **strikes against geoengineering** projects that were done without consultation of their communities. ([source](#) - p. 24)

→ In France, near the city of Lille, the Hellemmes-Ronchin reception area was established to serve as **temporary accommodation** for gens du voyage (traveller communities) passing through the region. However, since its inception, families have **settled there permanently** due to the **lack of viable alternatives**, a trend seen in many reception areas across France. The **women’s collective** of Hellemmes-Ronchin was formed in order to **achieve recognition of the health issues tied to pollution in the area**, as well as raising awareness of the **environmental racism** traveller communities in France face. ([source](#), p. 27)

→ **Just Stop Oil protesters** disrupted **pride** in London, England in 2023 due to polluters sponsoring the event. The protestors stated that these corporations were using pride to promote a good public image, which is in direct tension with the fact that **queer communities in the Global South** often bear the brunt of climate change. ([source](#))

→ **Environment and Development Action (ENDA) Colombia** works with **women recyclers / waste pickers** to understand the **unique challenges** they face (e.g., violence in working on the street). These collectives **challenge existing capitalist models** and promote solidarity economy models. ([source](#) - p.35)

→ **Honor the Earth** is an **indigenous ecofeminist organisation** in the USA that campaigns against sexual violence in extraction zones. In the **Brakken oil fields, North Dakota** and the **Tar Sands of Alberta**, extractivist **violence against nature** runs parallel to **violence against Indigenous** women. The collective requested a **formal intervention** by the **United Nations** and their submission document provides **research on the relationship between oil booms and sex trafficking**. ([source](#) - p. 87)

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Checklist One: How to draft a Gender Transformative Report

Checklist Summary

Positionality

- Where am I speaking from?
- What people/organisations have been present in the work here?
- Are we all on the same page?

Accessibility

- Who is the audience of this document?
- Have I taken steps to ensure this document is readable by everybody?

Applicability

- What contexts am I extrapolating to?
- Who am I assuming is the default person in the report writing?

What is a Gender Transformative Report?

Reports reflect the **positionalities** and the **politics** of the **people** and **organisations** who produce them. It is important when drafting a report that you have considered how to express your work in a way that **takes into consideration these positionalities**. It is **okay** if you have **not managed to address all power relations/structures** of inequality in your work! Transformative report writing is about **acknowledging** this and **expressing** your work in a way that **makes sense of what you have done** for both yourself and the reader.

Questions to ask yourself before writing

Positionality

Where am I speaking from?

You can start by asking yourself about your own position in relation to the topic at hand. What is your **personal interest** in the topic? How is this informed by your **experiences**? What are the **main theoretical approaches/understandings** you are drawing on? What **people/organisations have been present** in the work here?

Your work is not just based on your own personal politics but also the **politics of your organisation** and those who fund you. For example, if you are **based in the EU** and you are writing a research report on the **Western Balkans**, this would represent different dynamics than if you were writing about research conducted in **North Africa**. Whilst your work will often have a **disclaimer** saying it does not represent the views of the funder, it is still vital to **reflect on the purpose of your work**. For example, if you were doing EU funded research in the Western Balkans, are the outcomes affected by the **EU accession process**? In North Africa, would **colonial dynamics between researcher and subject** - that need to be reflected upon - be present?

Are we all on the same page?

If you are writing with **multiple authors**, it is good to **reflect on the questions in this checklist beforehand** and discuss **common definitions** of terms that will be used. By having a common understanding of definitions that reflect your positionality, you will not only produce work that is **clear** but also create a space for **productive dialogue** during the writing process.

Accessibility

Who is the audience of this document?

Thinking about the audience of the document is commonplace in research writing, but in order to apply feminist practices to this, you should reflect on **what you are assuming about your audience**. For example, are they **fluent in English**? Are they **familiar with** the words or **jargon** you use in your work? It is important to **always spell out jargon**, and if you have the funding - **pay somebody to translate your work** into multiple languages, depending on your audience's demands.

As **feminist theorist bell hooks** argues in their work "**Feminist theory from margin to center**", transformative writing should be **easily understood by a wide range of people** regardless of background:

A feminist essay with revolutionary ideas written in a complicated, abstract manner using the jargon of a specific discipline, will not have the impact it should have on the consciousness of women and men because it will probably be read by only a small group of people. (hooks, 1984 p. 111)

Have I taken steps to ensure this document is readable by everybody?

Accessibility is not just about jargon and ensuring you speak in plain English, but also considering the fact that **not everyone accesses documents in the same way**. For example, people who use **screen readers** benefit from having **image descriptions** of the pictures in your report so the screen reader can describe them. Similarly, **certain fonts and colours are more accessible than others**. Choose font colours that **contrast** with the **background** so they are readable, and fonts that are **not in cursive** (e.g., **sans serif** or **arial** are accessible fonts).

Applicability

What contexts am I extrapolating to?

There is a tendency in **European thinking** to imagine that our research can "**teach**" people from **outside Europe**. This **must be unlearnt** if we are to engage properly with the role of the EU in **colonial epistemic production**. E.g., if you are writing a report on EU environmental policy with NGOs based in Europe, you **should not claim to have applicability** to contexts you do not know – **unless you can prove** these tangible links.

Moreover, it is important to think about **why** you would imagine that lessons learnt in a specific context in Europe would be beneficial elsewhere? Viewing the EU as a place in which **universal lessons can be learnt**, whereas **abroad is considered "local"** or specific case studies, **reproduces colonial dynamics**.

Who am I assuming is the default person in the report writing?

Often feminist critique will highlight how there is a "**default man**" that pervades our thinking e.g., the assumption that being a **white, non-disabled, middle class European man** is the norm. This can also be reflected in **Eurocentric thinking**, for example talking about "**citizens**" of certain places **excludes stateless people or refugees**, or when projects that focus on democracy say that people are "**losing faith in the EU**" ignores the fact that the **EU from its inception was not built to represent marginalised groups**.

Checklist Two: Using Gender Transformative Language

Language is constantly evolving, and it is okay if you do not always use the most transformative language. The following sections reflect discussions on progressive language from queer, disability, and racial justice activists. Reflecting on the terms you use and keeping up to date with best practices ensures your language is clear, inclusive and indicates to the reader your positionality.

Disability Language

It is always best to **follow the lead of people with disabilities** when using **disability-first or person-first language**. When writing reports, it is important to use language that is both **specific and not patronising**. For example, use **"blind person"** rather than "visually challenged". Similarly, you **should not reduce people to their disability aids**, e.g., somebody is a **"wheelchair user"** not "wheelchair-bound". **Avoid** using terms such as **"able-bodied"** which implies that people with disabilities have bodies that do not work. It is also a **common trend to refer to policy documents as "blind"** e.g., "the European Green Deal is gender-blind". **Avoid such language** and use terms such as **"does not account for"** or **"ignorant of"** instead.

Remember! It is our world that has never been made accessible for people with disabilities, the onus is not on those with disabilities themselves to conform to ableist structures.

Vulnerabilities Language

Avoid using terms such as "vulnerable people" or "poor people" that puts emphasis on people themselves. **No one is inherently vulnerable**; this language creates a **dichotomy of "us and them"**. **Structures of discrimination create vulnerable situations**. Calling someone vulnerable can also be used as a **domination technique** and diminish people's feeling of **agency**. Preferable terms to use instead are those that put emphasis on the structure: e.g., **people from marginalised groups, disproportionately affected groups, structurally excluded, or people living in vulnerable situations**.

Remember! When talking about aging groups "elderly" implies a dependency/inability and is often used to typecast whole generations, using older persons is preferred by activists.

Racialisation

Using the term **"racialised groups"** is preferable to "race" as it shows that race is socially constructed by highlighting the process of racialisation. **Equinox** defines **"racialised people"** as **"individuals and groups who have been subject to a process of racialisation and been ascribed a particular racial category"**. In European societies, **all people are racialised**, however we use the term to refer to those that have been **negatively racialised or racialised as "other"**.

Geographies

Describing the world through development discourse has **undergone a lot of changes**. **During the Cold War**, the terms **first, second and third world** were used to refer to the capitalist **coloniser** countries, **communist**, and **colonised** countries respectively. These descriptions have been criticised for creating a **heirarchy** between groups of countries. **After the Cold War**, the terms **Global North** and **South** became popular to describe countries that were **colonisers** versus those that **were colonised**, with **Global East** being used to describe the countries that were **subject to Russian imperialism**.

Core, periphery, and **semi-periphery** are **Marxist terms** that are used to describe how the **core countries colonised the periphery countries** in order to **violently extract wealth, resources and persons** from them for the core's own development. In this construction the **semi-periphery** is the **eastern European** countries which serve as a **reserve** for colonial extraction. Whilst the Cold War dynamics have shifted considerably, **these term is still used by some decolonial Marxists**.

Global Majority is a term used to describe **Black, Indigenous, and People of Colour** – who make up the **majority** of the **world's population**. **Global Minority** refers to **white** people, who despite being in the minority **violently dominate** with **white supremacy**.

Remember! It is important to discuss which framing you use whenever you are writing. Look at the context and see which framing you think applies best.

Non-Binary Language

Always write in gender neutral language, it is important to be **specific** about who you are speaking about and **highlight the social construction of gender**. For example, if you were writing a report about the gendered effects of toxic chemicals, you can write "**people who are assigned male or female at birth**". This highlights that we are **given a sex at birth** based on **sex characteristics** but that this **does not determine our gender**. Whereas terms like "**women**" refer to the **social elements** of a gendered group of individuals.

Remember! If you are writing a report and your data is only about women, it is not beneficial to tack onto the end "and nonbinary people/ marginalised genders" if this is not part of your analysis. Inclusion for the sake of it is not beneficial.

Avoiding saviourism and empowerment

When discussing empowerment, it is important **we do not use it as a buzzword**, for example **vague statements about 'empowering' groups** can often come from a **saviourist** standpoint which is not helpful. Additionally, **people cannot be empowered out of the structures that oppress them**, so any discussion of empowerment should be in **parallel with addressing such structures** otherwise the **onus is left on the individual**. "**Agents of change**" is an **alternative conceptualisation** to "empowerment". Recognising the agency of a person, means that you listen to what they have to say, and you **respect their experiences and knowledge**. An agent of change is working to **create systemic change** for themselves and their community. You cannot give a voice to someone who already has a voice, but you can **lend them your megaphone** and give them your seat at the decision-making table.

Remember! The images you use in a document are key signifiers and often reproduce power relations. It is important that you do not use tokenistic images i.e., using images of people from a marginalised community just to portray diversity that your work does not possess.

FURTHER READING

Equinox (2021) [Towards Gender Justice](#)

Gorman, J. (2024) [Beyond Extractivism in Research with Communities and Movements](#), The Commons Social Change Library

Decolonialidad Europa (2013) [Charter of Decolonial Research Ethics](#)

Sze, J.S., Cosmopolis, C., Hubbard, E.R.C., Mani, S., and Wang, M.M.H (2024) Challenging Colonial Practices in Research: A Guide for PhD Researchers, UK Research Integrity Office

Women Enabled International (2024) [Glossary](#)

Women Engage for a Common Future (2024) [Gender Glossary](#)

